

TOWARDS STRAIN-BASED STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING OF A COMPOSITE AIRFOIL UNDER UNCERTAINTY

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1 General introduction

Sensitive/ high risk structures should be carefully designed such that catastrophic failures can be avoided. Traditionally this is achieved by considering safety factors and following “safe life” or “fail safe” design strategies to create a margin between real-time operational loadings and residual strengths remaining in structural materials [1]. Although these methodologies have been used for many years, the increasing impact of economic considerations and emerging inspection technologies have historically led designers to arrive at new strategies such as the “damage tolerance” approach; however, some inherent limitations still persisted in the latter strategy such as the absence of continuous health assessments [1]. In more recent years, the advancement of non-destructive inspection technologies, economical limitations and historical catastrophic failures directed designers to the introduction of the concept of Structural Health Monitoring (SHM). Essentially, SHM is an integration of sensing and possibly actuation devices within a structure to allow the loading and damage state of the structure during service to be monitored, recorded, analyzed, localized, quantified and predicted. Thus, non-destructive testing becomes an integral part of the system [1, 2]. A typical SHM structure is shown in Figure 1.

The concept of Structural Health Monitoring can also be closely linked to four other subjects: Condition Monitoring of rotating and reciprocating machines, Nondestructive evaluation techniques, Statistical Process Control and Damage Prognosis [2-4]. Condition Monitoring (CM) has a long history in the field of damage monitoring for rotating and reciprocating machines, and owing to some well-developed databases, successful monitoring systems have been introduced and applied in different

industries. Nondestructive testing (NDT) is analogous (though not identical) to Structural Health Monitoring, as it is carried out offline, locally or globally, and trained technicians and scheduled maintenance programs are required. Statistical Process Control (SPC) deals with the techniques that statistically monitor the behavior of a process and control its quality. SPC is signal-based rather than structure-based, and analyzes raw data transmitted from distributed sensors to monitor abnormalities and estimates the cause of changes. Damage Prognosis (DP) algorithms are used to predict the remaining life-time of a structure after current damage distributions in the structure has been established using SHM techniques. SHM is fundamentally based on NDT techniques combined with efficient programming and signal processing methods; but additional restrictions limit the number of developed NDTs that can be used as the pillar for making an accurate and reliable SHM system [2].

In brief, Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) has been widely applied in different industrial sectors including condition monitoring of machinery, oil platforms, railways, civil infrastructures and aeronautical engineering [1-18]. The technology promises to reduce the required safety factors and extend the interval between manual inspections by providing continuous automated monitoring throughout the life of a given structure.

2 Motivation and objective of this study

A major concern in developing any robust and reliable SHM system would be the effect of uncertainty of input parameters on the correctness of output/damage predictions. On other hand, current computer aided SHM tools increasingly rely on engineering simulations and modeling tools for a

wide range of applications. Hence, next to the effect of uncertainty of physical parameters, the modeling process itself can put the performance and accuracy of the output/predictions at risk at different levels of a SHM development process. The uncertainty in practice may come from sensing systems by means of inaccurate data transmitted from sensors or an imprecise database during the damage signature development process, manufacturing errors (such as not fully controlled material deposition in a mould), environmental noises, loading perturbations, or the feature extraction/classification tool boxes. All these sources could yield an SHM system that is occasionally misleading with possible false alarms.

An earlier study [5] using numerical simulations showed that the inclusion of sources of uncertainty in a SHM can be crucial, specifically since the variation caused in the response of a structure due to uncertainty sources could be as large as those by the damage itself. Namely, the structure in that investigation was a composite T-joint which was earlier introduced in [6] and used to launch a strain-based SHM program (called GNAISPIN) with the aid of MATLAB and NASTRAN-PATRAN. Figure 2 shows a schematic of the above T-joint composite structure. In [5], fiber orientations in the bulkhead, hull and overlaminates as well as the pull-off loading offset of the T-joint were considered as four main potential sources of uncertainty and their effects were evaluated via a Design-of-Experiment (DOE) method along with a series of ANOVA analysis and an ABAQUS model. Results in [5] clearly showed that *the absolute effect of individual manufacturing uncertainty factors in deviating the structure's response under loading can be as high as that caused by the presence of delamination* when compared to the response of the healthy case even in the absence of manufacturing error. Another interesting conclusion in that study was that, statistically, the relative significance of noise factors would be nearly identical in the healthy and damaged structures.

The aim of the present article is to investigate the importance of considering uncertainty due to materials/manufacturing errors in another composite structure and loading condition: a commonly used NACA-0012 airfoil under tensile loading (Figure 3). The airfoil is a sandwich structure containing a 3 mm thick PVC foam, reinforced with E-glass and carbon woven fabrics (Table 1). The prototype is vacuum bagged and elastic material properties of its components were estimated based on [7-9] (Table 2). The structure was first tested under a pre-defined set of different delamination scenarios (more details in Section 3)

under static tensile loading. Then, a finite element (FE) model of the test was established, validated, and used for further analysis as a virtual experimental tool to create more damage scenarios with varying ply thicknesses (mimicking a manufacturing error). Eventually, via ANOVA analyses, statistical significances of the uncertainty factor on SHM predictions have been captured. An advantage of this study, compared to earlier modeling works such as [5], is that the range of uncertainty directly estimated based on random repeats of actual/physical tests.

3 Experiments and finite element model

Over twenty different types of defect have been reported in the literature for composite structures [10-18]. Here, the focus is on the most common defect mode in sandwich structures which is delamination. Delamination itself, considering the origin of its initiation, may be caused by low energy impact, stress concentration at free surfaces, stress concentration due to tabbed joints, machining, poor curing process, etc. In this work, artificial delaminations were embedded into the test samples by inserting a waxed thin plate between the corresponding plies during the airfoil prototyping process, regardless of the cause of such damage mode. Five different damage scenarios (delamination location/configuration) were initially considered as illustrated in Figure 4. Figures 5, 6 and 7 illustrate, respectively, the force-displacement behavior of the airfoils with no damage, damage at the leading edge versus that at the trailing edge, damage at the quarter chord up to the PVC foam versus damage at the quarter chord down to the PVC foam. Figure 5 indicates a lack of performance repeatability of the structure under the same manufacturing process (which can be attributed to uncontrollable factors/noise during fabrication; here thickness non-uniformity due to applying resin rich or starvation regions during manual lay-up). Also from Figure 6 it is evident that the structure's stiffness in the presence of damage closer to the trailing edge (with a sharp geometrical corner) is more reduced.

The tensile test results were then employed to establish and validate a FE model of the structure (Figure 8). Figures 9 and 10 compare the force-displacement curves corresponding to the samples with no damage (healthy scenario) and delamination at the trailing edge based on the average data obtained from the experiments and the finite element model. A good agreement (with a mean residual error of 6%) between the experiments and numerical

simulations was obtained and allowed the further use of the developed FE code as a virtual experimental tool to create more damage scenarios and uncertainty simulations. It should be mentioned that in Figures 9 experimental curves correspond to the average behavior observed for different samples subjected to the same loading. It will be shown later (Figure 11) that with embedding the uncertainty in the FE model, the upper and lower limits of the scatter in the experimental data (i.e., the three repeats of the test) can also be captured.

Table 3 shows the displacement variations at different loading values for the tested airfoils with no delamination (i.e., using data in Figure 5). We assume that these variations in the structure's global response have been equivalently caused by variations in thickness of different plies (carbon 200 gr/m³ and glass 200 gr/m³; both below and above the PVC foam), which is a common case during hand lay-up processes. Subsequently, the FE code was used with an inverse method to determine a reasonable thickness range for each of the above-mentioned plies to cover at least 60% of experimental data scatter (Table 4). The lower and upper thickness limits provided in Table 4 were then used to generate random values (assuming a uniform distribution) for each ply thicknesses in the subsequent stochastic simulations. Figure 11 shows the example of simulated response variation via the randomness in ply-2 thicknesses versus that of the actual tensile tests on the healthy structure.

4 Sensitivity analysis of damage vs. uncertainty

As addressed in Section 2, the main purpose of this study was to systematically determine the importance of manufacturing uncertainty sources, here in the form of ply thickness variations, on the reliability of the damage signature database (DSB) that can be used in future studies to develop a robust strain-based SHM tool for the NACA0012 airfoil. In this regard, using the identified ply thickness variations in Table 4 (as input), the corresponding variations of the strain distribution (as output) on the lower surface of the airfoil was statistically analysed to determine the exact amount of disturbance caused by the thickness variation compared to that caused by the presence of delamination at different locations (delamination length in all cases was 2 cm). Four different cases were considered: model with no delamination (healthy) and models with single delamination at the leading edge, quarter chord below the PVC foam and the trailing edge. The internal chord of the 3D airfoil is 31cm and the

external chord is 33.5cm. Fifteen positions along the lower surface of the airfoil were considered as sensing points to estimate an accurate (continuous) strain distribution pattern. Figure 12 shows the corresponding sensor points at which the horizontal strain values have been collected in each FE simulation. Table 5 shows randomly selected thickness values used for different plies in the stochastic FE simulations (note that each ply thickness has an upper and lower bound as indicated in Table 4). For each damage scenario, these stochastic repeats (R1 to R5) were simulated and strain values for sensors 1-15 were collected (Figure 13) and used for statistical analysis.

Table 6 shows the ensuing strain values at sensor 1, followed by the corresponding two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). The mean sum of squares (variance) of the strain response due to damage scenarios at this sensor location is 2.448E-09 which is about 1 order of magnitude less than the corresponding variance caused by thickness variation (1.975E-08). Therefore, the ANOVA analysis here suggests that for this point the effect of variation of the ply thickness (manufacturing uncertainty) is at least one order of magnitude more significant compared to the variation caused by the presence or position of delamination. This conclusion can be further proven according to the p-values for the damage and thickness variation treatments in Table 6: the p-value for thickness variation is close to zero (0.003167), while the p-value for damage scenarios is 0.466137. Hence, with a statistical significance level of $\alpha=5\%$ (or a 95% confidence level), it can be inferred that only thickness variation is the significant factor for this sensor and it is not sensitive to damage scenario variations.

Next, the above statistical analysis was repeated for all the 15 sensors. For some sensors such as sensors 2 to 5, the analysis resulted in an opposite conclusion to that of sensor 1: the damage in these sensors was statistically significant and the thickness variation acts as an insignificant manufacturing noise with a p-value greater than 5%. For instance, from Table 7, at sensor 2 the p-value calculated with respect to the variance caused by the damage scenarios is 0.0004 which indicates a very significant sensitivity of this sensor location to damage factor (even more than sensor 1), while the high p-value of 0.1129 observed for the thickness variation effect shows that this sensor location can be reliably used for DSB training sets during a robust SHM development.

From the summary of all sensitivity analyses in Table 8, it can be seen that sensors 3 and 5 similarly proved that they are robust against thickness variation and most sensitive to the presence and location of damage. At sensor 4, the damage and thickness factors are comparably of the same statistical significance which would make the weight of this sensing point less (but still acceptable) for damage identification. Sensors 6-15 show a very high p-value with respect to the damage factor and hence may receive less weight during SHM training.

5 Conclusions

Uncertainty is an inevitable part of a design process for most structural health monitoring systems. In this article, preliminary steps were taken toward a robust pattern recognition technique capable of considering uncertainty perturbations in a hand lay-upped and vacuum bagged composite airfoil. The established FE model under quasi-static tensile loading was used as a virtual experimental tool to perform more detailed statistical analysis on the effect of thickness variations as a representative manufacturing uncertainty source. The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) evaluated the importance of considering uncertainty on the strain distribution pattern at different sensor positions. For most of the strain nodes, the effect of variation in the thickness factor was more significant than the variation caused by the presence of the damage itself; hence, raising the point that uncertainty analysis prior to the development of any robust SHM system is a vital stage in order to arrive at a reliable damage signature database (DSB) that is less sensitive to uncertainty and more to the damage.

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Figure 1. Example of an SHM system [2]

Figure 2. Schematic of the T-joint composite structure considered in the studies [5] and [6]

Figure 3. The composite airfoil sample under tension

Table 1. Stacking sequence of the airfoil and nominal ply thicknesses

Layer no.	Type	Density (gr/m ²)	~ Thickness (mm)
1	E-glass (woven)	50	0.06
2	E-glass (woven)	200	0.2
3	E-glass (woven)	200	0.2
4	Carbon (woven)	200	0.2
5	PVC foam	80	3.0
6	Carbon (woven)	200	0.2
7	E-glass (woven)	200	0.2
8	E-glass (woven)	200	0.2
9	E-glass (woven)	50	0.06

Table 2. The material properties used for modeling the airfoil plies (x- index refers to the main fiber direction; woven fabrics in FE simulations were modeled as a cross-ply laminate)

	Young's Modulus (MPa)	Poisson's Ratio	Shear Modulus (MPa)
CFRP	$E_x = 62000$	$\nu_{xy} = 0.22$	$G_{xy} = 3270$
	$E_y = 4800$	$\nu_{xz} = 0.22$	$G_{xz} = 3270$
	$E_z = 4800$	$\nu_{yz} = 0.30$	$G_{yz} = 1860$
GFRP	$E_x = 21000$	$\nu_{xy} = 0.26$	$G_{xy} = 1520$
	$E_y = 7000$	$\nu_{xz} = 0.26$	$G_{xz} = 1520$
	$E_z = 7000$	$\nu_{yz} = 0.30$	$G_{yz} = 2650$

Figure 4. The embedded damage scenarios during prototyping of the airfoil

Figure 5. Repeats of the tensile test for three different airfoil samples with no embedded delamination (healthy case)

Figure 6. Mean force-displacement response for two damage scenarios: damage at the leading edge versus damage at the trailing edge

Figure 7. Mean force-displacement response for two damage scenarios: damage at the quarter chord up to the PVC foam versus damage at quarter chord down to the PVC foam

Figure 8. Sample result from the finite element simulation of the structure under tensile loading

Figure 9. Comparing the average experimental and numerical force-displacement curves for the airfoil with no damage

Figure 10. Comparing the average experimental and numerical force-displacement curves for the airfoil with delamination at the trailing edge (position # 3 as shown in Figure 4)

Table 3. Variation of displacement observed at different load magnitudes for different samples using experimental data in Figure 5

Load	min Disp.	max Disp.	difference %	mean (mm)
500	0.222	0.349	36.3	0.285
1000	0.465	0.692	32.8	0.579
1500	0.757	1.058	28.4	0.907
2000	1.072	1.479	27.5	1.275
2500	1.403	1.668	15.9	1.535

Table 4. Calculated thickness ranges (in cm) of different composite layers to cover about 60% of the variation observed in the experiments in Figure 5.

t2 - Glass200 - below PVC foam				
Load	t2 - min	Displacement (t2 - min)	t2 - max	Displacement (t2 - max)
500	0.18	0.3442	0.4	0.2812
1000	0.18	0.6885	0.4	0.5625
1500	0.18	1.033	0.4	0.8437
2000	0.18	1.377	0.4	1.125
2500	0.18	1.511	0.4	1.406
t3 - Carbon200 - below PVC foam				
Load	t3 - min	Displacement (t3 - min)	t3 - max	Displacement (t3 - max)
500	0.2	0.3441	0.4	0.2807
1000	0.2	0.6883	0.4	0.5614
1500	0.2	1.033	0.4	0.8421
2000	0.2	1.378	0.4	1.123
2500	0.2	1.59	0.4	1.403
t4 - Carbon200 - above PVC foam				
Load	t4 - min	Displacement (t4 - min)	t4 - max	Displacement (t4 - max)
500	0.16	0.3455	0.28	0.2808
1000	0.17	0.6919	0.28	0.5616
1500	0.17	1.038	0.28	0.8424
2000	0.17	1.384	0.28	1.123
2500	0.2	1.59	0.28	1.404
t5 - Glass200 - above PVC foam				
Load	t5 - min	Displacement (t5 - min)	t5 - max	Displacement (t5 - max)
500	0.16	0.3466	0.3	0.2803
1000	0.16	0.6932	0.3	0.5605
1500	0.16	1.04	0.3	0.8408
2000	0.16	1.386	0.3	1.121
2500	0.2	1.59	0.3	1.401

Figure 11. Upper and lower limits of the scatter in the experimental data vs. those captured by the stochastic FE model using t2-tickness variation

Figure 12. The position of virtual sensors 1-15 (i.e., the strain measurement nodes in the FE model)

Table 5. Randomly selected thickness values for different plies

	Glass 200 below PVC foam	Carbon 200 below PVC foam	Glass 200 above PVC foam	Carbon 200 above PVC foam
Repeats	t2 (cm)	t3 (cm)	t4 (cm)	t5 (cm)
R1	0.31	0.29	0.21	0.29
R2	0.38	0.21	0.20	0.21
R3	0.23	0.26	0.19	0.20
R4	0.38	0.31	0.24	0.27
R5	0.23	0.39	0.21	0.26

Figure 13. Strain distribution along the lower surface of the healthy airfoil for the five random repeats using thickness values in Table 5

Table 6. Strain values and the corresponding ANOVA analysis at sensor 1 under different damage scenarios and random repeats according to Table 5

Damage scenario	Repeat#1	Repeat#2	Repeat#3	Repeat#4	Repeat#5
Healthy	3.13E-04	3.48E-04	3.48E-04	2.57E-04	2.87E-04
Leading edge	3.04E-04	5.57E-04	4.28E-04	2.49E-04	2.77E-04
Chord Down	3.13E-04	3.44E-04	4.39E-04	2.57E-04	2.86E-04
Trailing edge	3.13E-04	3.44E-04	4.39E-04	2.57E-04	2.86E-04
ANOVA for Sensor 1					
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Damage	7.345E-09	3	2.448E-09	0.90762061	0.466137
Thickness	7.901E-08	4	1.975E-08	7.32279813	0.003167
Error	3.237E-08	12	2.697E-09		
Total	1.187E-07	19			

Table 7. Strain values and the corresponding ANOVA analysis at sensor 2 under different damage scenarios and random repeats according to Table 5

Damage scenario	Repeat#1	Repeat#2	Repeat#3	Repeat#4	Repeat#5
Healthy	3.00E-04	3.31E-04	3.31E-04	3.21E-04	2.97E-04
Leading edge	1.72E-04	3.35E-04	1.34E-04	2.14E-04	1.55E-04
Chord Down	3.08E-04	3.37E-04	3.30E-04	3.28E-04	3.05E-04
Trailing edge	3.08E-04	3.37E-04	3.30E-04	3.28E-04	3.05E-04
ANOVA for Sensor 2					
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value
Damage	5.19E-08	3	1.73E-08	13.10	0.00
Thickness	1.24E-08	4	3.104E-09	2.35	0.11
Error	1.58E-08	12	1.32E-09		
Total	8.02E-08	19			

Table 8. Summary of all sensitivity analyses for sensors 1-15 against the damage and thickness variation factors

	Source of Variation	F-statistics	P-value	this sensor is MORE sensitive to
Sensor 1	Damage status	0.9076	0.4661	Thickness variation
	Thickness variation	7.3228	0.0032	
Sensor 2	Damage status	13.1039	0.0004	Damage
	Thickness variation	2.3508	0.1129	
Sensor 3	Damage status	33.4626	0.0000	Damage
	Thickness variation	3.7305	0.0339	
Sensor 4	Damage status	4.6204	0.0227	Damage
	Thickness variation	4.6260	0.0172	
Sensor 5	Damage status	44.8866	0.0000	Damage
	Thickness variation	2.6817	0.0830	
Sensor 6	Damage status	0.9286	0.4567	Thickness variation
	Thickness variation	3.1116	0.0567	
Sensor 7	Damage status	1.0118	0.4214	Thickness variation
	Thickness variation	3.0952	0.0575	
Sensor 8	Damage status	1.0291	0.4144	Thickness variation
	Thickness variation	3.1273	0.0560	
Sensor 9	Damage status	1.0403	0.4099	Thickness variation
	Thickness variation	3.1583	0.0545	
Sensor 10	Damage status	1.0316	0.4134	Thickness variation
	Thickness variation	3.1322	0.0557	
Sensor 11	Damage status	1.0091	0.4225	Thickness variation
	Thickness variation	3.0732	0.0586	
Sensor 12	Damage status	0.9971	0.4274	Thickness variation
	Thickness variation	3.0782	0.0584	
Sensor 13	Damage status	1.0767	0.3958	Thickness variation
	Thickness variation	3.3397	0.0467	
Sensor 14	Damage status	1.1128	0.3822	Thickness variation
	Thickness variation	4.0818	0.0258	
Sensor 15	Damage status	0.8883	0.4750	Thickness variation
	Thickness variation	7.2305	0.0033	